

Study of adsorption of methylene blue on TiO₂ in the aqueous solution containing salts of magnetism and calcium at high concentration

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Abstract : The adsorption of pollutants onto anatase TiO₂ is a key stage in the photodegradation process and shows different effects under various conditions. The adsorption of methylene blue (MB) onto TiO₂ was investigated using TiO₂ particle suspensions containing high salt concentrations. The intensity of the MB adsorption and ionic association were determined via total organic carbon (TOC) and molar conductivity measurements, respectively. UV-Vis spectrometry experiments showed that the particles were nanosized anatase TiO₂ in the suspension. Adsorption increased the quantity of the MB dimer and the MB suspension was stable when the salt concentration was equal to or greater than 0.5 M, which also showed that the experimental results were independent of aggregation. All of the adsorption trends initially increased to a maximum value; then, the adsorption slightly decreased for a few minutes before reaching equilibrium. However, differences existed for the different salt concentration ranges. From 1–3 M, increasing the temperature decreased the equilibrium time; beyond 3 M, the adsorption capability slightly increased; from 3–5 M, the adsorption rate decreased much faster than in the other ranges, and a hindering adsorption effect was observed in the following order : Mg²⁺ > Ca²⁺. The mechanism is also discussed in detail.

Keywords : MB, TiO₂, adsorption, salt concentration, UV-Vis spectroscopy.

Introduction

Since the initial research by Fujishima and Honda in 1972¹, there has been increasing interest in pollutant removal via photocatalysis, particularly TiO₂ photocatalysis. Colloidal nanosized TiO₂ powder was often used because it was much more effective than an immobilised system due to its higher available surface area.

Methylene blue (MB) is a typical dye used in the printing and dyeing industry and is also often used as an indicator in photocatalysis experiments. Its molecular formula is C₁₆H₁₈ClN₃S·3(H₂O). Inorganic salts, such as MgCl₂ and CaCl₂, that are extensively used as auxiliary agents can be present in very high concentration with dyes in printing and dyeing wastewater. The discharge of highly coloured wastewater into the ecosystem causes serious environmental problems. Photocatalysis has been considered an effective means for purifying wastewater,

and the published works on the photocatalysis mechanism underline that the key stages are the surface reactions between the photocatalyst and adsorbed species^{2,3}. In most cases, the enhanced photoactivity of semiconductors has contributed to their superior adsorption capacity⁴. Thus, Cl⁻ retardation of the photocatalysis is generally explained as a competitor of the substrate adsorption that reduces photoactivity^{5,6}. However, Mg²⁺ and Ca²⁺ have no influence on the photocatalytic degradation (PCD) of trichlorfon and glyphosate^{7,8} and promote the PCD of humic acid⁹; these phenomena can also be attributed to the influence of the substrate adsorption. Therefore, detailed research of the real state of adsorption as the key step in photocatalysis is necessary.

During the past few years, several studies on adsorption intensity measurements^{10,11}, regeneration¹², differing structure¹³ and influence of inorganic salt^{14,15} on TiO₂ have been published. It is noteworthy that the ionic strength

was reported as an important parameter for the adsorption of substrates, such as dyes, onto the oxide surface¹⁶; however, very little research has been conducted on the adsorption of substrate in solution containing high inorganic salt concentrations. The only experiments involved substrate photocatalysis related to adsorption with inorganic salt concentrations below 1 M^{17,18}. Therefore, it is interesting to investigate the role of substrate adsorption onto TiO₂ in the aqueous salt solutions of higher concentrations.

In this work, we investigated the adsorption of MB

onto nanosized TiO₂ in aqueous suspensions containing high concentrations of MgCl₂ or CaCl₂. The aim of this research was to investigate the variety in the adsorption of the suspension.

Results and discussion

Fig. 1 shows the UV-Vis absorption spectrum from the study and indicates that the onset wavelength for the TiO₂ absorption was 380 nm, which reveals that the TiO₂ particle nanosized in the anatase phase because the absorption wavelength of such particles is always between 350–400 nm¹⁹⁻²¹. Fig. 1 also illustrates that the absorp-

Fig. 1. Variations in the absorbance vs wavelength for a TiO₂ suspension without MB (a), a MB solution without TiO₂ (b) and a TiO₂ suspension with MB (c) (T = 25 °C).

tion spectrums of (a) and (b) nearly compose those of (c). The other cases in this study showed the same conditions.

These phenomena indicate that the adsorption did not influence the structure of either the MB or the TiO₂. However, the adsorption peak at 620 nm present in (c) indicates that the MB dimer concentration increased upon adsorption. It could be concluded that the adsorption might assemble MB onto the TiO₂ surface and thus cause its association.

Fig. 2(a) shows the strong linear relationship between the absorbance at 308 nm and TiO₂ concentration. Plots of the TiO₂ particle sedimentation as a function of time based on this relationship are shown in Fig. 2(b). These data show that the nanoparticles settled out of solution as a function of time and salt concentration. We noted that the nanoparticle suspensions are stable in the presence of MB when the salt concentration is equal to or greater than 0.5 M. Only the nanoparticle suspensions without

salt were unstable.

The results^{22,23} indicate that the stability of the colloidal system is determined by the sum of the van der Waals attractive and electrical double layer (EDL) forces between the particles as they approach one another due to Brownian motion. Though the addition of salt can hinder the electrostatic repulsion by compressing the (EDL), too high of a salt concentration can reinforce the EDL and solution polarity, thus inhibiting the attractive van der Waals forces. In the water with only MB (which is nearly equal to the pH_{ZPC} for the TiO₂ nanoparticles), the surface charge was nearly neutral, and the EDL was nearly zero. Therefore, the attractive van der Waals forces dominate, which increases the aggregation.

Because of its ionisation in water, adsorbed MB might bring positively charge onto TiO₂ surface in aqueous solutions, which could strengthen or reduce the EDL; however, its concentration was too low relative to the salt and

Fig. 2. Variation of the absorbance at 308 nm vs the TiO₂ concentration with MB (a), variation of the absorbance vs time in different solutions with MB (b) (T = 25 °C).

TiO₂ to observe this influence. These results indicate that it is not necessary to consider the influence of the dye charge on the surface of the nanoscale TiO₂ in photocatalysis if the dye concentration is low; they also demonstrate that our experimental results were independent of the TiO₂ aggregation.

Fig. 3(a) and (b) show the amount of adsorbed MB versus time for different MgCl₂ and CaCl₂ concentrations. The amount of adsorbed MB increased with the reducing for the number of potential adsorption sites on the TiO₂ particle surfaces. Once all of the sites are occupied, the adsorption concentration becomes constant, and a monolayer forms in agreement with the Langmuir adsorption model^{24,25}. The quantity of the adsorbed molecules observe initially increased to a maximum value, decreased slightly for a few minutes and then reached equilibrium. We concluded that the charge of the TiO₂ surface was positively charged at the experimental pH (<5.8) with numerous neutral sites. Below this value, the adsorption at the neutral sites was the primary effect; however, during the brief drop in adsorption, two other

effects occurred between the MB and TiO₂. First, based on the reported literature^{26,27}, the MB adsorbed onto the TiO₂ surface can dissociate slightly, especially in solutions containing high salt concentrations. Thus, electrostatic repulsion on the surface was reinforced, and the MB adsorption was blocked. Second, according to the polarity effect of the adsorbed substrate²⁸, the nitrogen and sulphur atoms in the MB molecule create a significant electric dipole moment that leads to the positively charged aromatic rings being electrostatically attracted to negatively charged particles, such as Cl⁻ and sulphur atoms in MB molecule, in the neighbouring site at a sufficiently high adsorption. This attraction strengthened the neutral state of the TiO₂ surface and favours adsorption. Beginning at the peak value, these two effects played the primary role in the adsorption. During the decreased adsorption, the first effect dominated the second until reaching an equilibrium, in which the two effects were equal.

Fig. 4(a) and (b) show that the molar conductivity rapidly dropped near salt concentrations of 3 M and remained constant at those above 5 M. These measurements

Fig. 3. Variation of MB adsorption rate vs time in MgCl₂ (a) and CaCl₂ (b) aqueous solution ($T = 25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$).

Fig. 4. Molar conductivity vs concentration of CaCl₂ or MgCl₂ without MB (a) and with MB (b) (T = 25 °C).

revealed an ionic association at salt concentrations above 3 M. This association was established within the range of 3–5 M and then maintained stability above 5 M. Indeed, the association influenced the adsorption and will be involved in the following discussion.

Fig. 5 shows that the adsorption capability of MB decreased with increasing salt concentrations. It could be assumed that the adsorption of Cl⁻ was competitive with MB, which results in MB adsorption decreasing with increasing salt concentrations. This result highlighted how the ions can influence the substrate adsorption and photocatalysis²⁹. Increasing the salt concentration can enhance the following two effects: the hindering of the MB adsorption and the ionic association that limits the ionic mobilities³⁰. Increasing the initial salt concentration caused a durative decrease in the MB adsorption, which is primarily due to such hindering. At the concentration between 3 M and 5 M, the adsorption rate rapidly dropped, and we conclude that the ionic associations formed by

molecules of MgCl₂, CaCl₂ or other ion association complexes on the TiO₂ surface did not have active ion mass transfers and elevated the steric hindrance between MB and the surface. In addition, increasing ion concentrations can strengthen the polarity, which also blocked adsorption.

MB adsorption still occurred during the experiments conducted in solutions with very high salt concentrations, and it could be assumed that at the lowest experimental pH (5.2), there were still numerous neutral sites on the TiO₂ surface, in which MB could be closer so that adsorption could occur. In addition, it is believed that the nanoparticle surface is very rough³¹, and some organic compounds adsorbed onto the TiO₂ particle can form inner-sphere complexes on the surface²⁶; therefore, it can also be believed that some MB adsorbed onto TiO₂ cannot be replaced by Cl⁻, although the salt concentration is very high.

To examine the influence of temperature, we selected

Fig. 5. Variation in the MB adsorption equilibrium rate vs the salt concentration (T = 25 °C).

several salt concentrations and varied the adsorption temperature from 20 to 80 °C. Based on previous studies^{28,32}, increasing the temperature was expected to improve the adsorption capability of the MB. In our experiments, the equilibrium times were shortened, as shown in Fig. 6. Indeed, elevating the temperature decreased the solution

viscosity and improved mass transfer. However, Fig. 7 shows approximately identical MB adsorption capabilities for salt concentrations from 1–3 M, which indicates that increasing the temperature does not accelerate the capabilities at lower Cl⁻ concentrations. Indeed, if the MB adsorption can be improved in that manner, Cl⁻ ab-

Fig. 6. Equilibration time vs temperature.

Fig. 7. Variation of the MB adsorption rate vs temperature in aqueous MgCl₂ (a) and CaCl₂ (b) solutions.

sorption should be further improved because it has better diffusivity due to its smaller volume. In addition, the higher quantity of Cl⁻ adsorbed onto the TiO₂ likely enhanced the stereospecific blockade. This result is inconsistent with previous research indicating that the thermodynamic approximation delineates the adsorption efficiency of the TiO₂ and could be accelerated by increased temperature²⁸ and indicates that improving the photocatalysis effect for wastewater with such complex components, such as ions at a certain concentration, by increasing temperature might be impossible.

Note that Fig. 7 also indicates that the MB adsorption capability increased slightly upon increasing the temperature at salt concentrations above 3 M. This phenomenon can be explained by the ionic association playing a more important role at concentrations above 3 M, as discussed above. Increasing the temperature prevented the associated matter from forming onto the TiO₂ surface because molecule or ionic migration was strengthened, which de-

creases the stereospecific blockade of contact between MB and TiO₂.

Dye adsorption strongly depends on the salt concentration and species because such ions influence the electrostatic parameters, such as the oxide surface charge and pH. The addition of identical concentrations of CaCl₂ and MgCl₂ were studied to highlight the effect of different cations had on the dye adsorption under identical Cl⁻ influences under the similar properties of Mg²⁺ and Ca²⁺. In addition, these salts were expected to be particularly influential in the high concentration solutions.

For salt concentrations ranging from 3–5 M, the amount of MB adsorbed on the TiO₂ surface in suspensions containing CaCl₂ was higher than for MgCl₂, as shown in Fig. 5. This result was related to the differences between Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ because the Cl⁻ concentration was constant, which highlights how the interactions between the TiO₂ surface and differing cations are specific to the nature of those cations³³. Indeed, Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ have the

same valency; however, Mg^{2+} has a stronger electrostatic field because of its smaller radius compared with Ca^{2+} . Following this reasoning, it is believed that the ionic associations between Mg^{2+} and the TiO_2 surface could better obstruct contact between MB and TiO_2 across the range of 3–5 M than Ca^{2+} because the electrostatic force of Mg^{2+} is stronger. In addition, the formations contained a stronger solvation shell around Mg^{2+} ³⁴ that could also better block large and tight hydrated molecules. However, the cation effect is nearly the same outside of this range because the ionic association are not obvious at lower concentrations and the effect of association was convergent at higher concentrations.

These assumptions explain the adsorption trends for the dye versus the Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} concentration observed in our experiments; however, it is difficult to hypothesise why the cations had an enhancing effect in other studies⁹. Indeed, when an ion of a given valency has a significant effect on the photocatalysis of a substrate, it must have a specific interaction with either the substrate or oxide³⁵, in contrast with the theory stated above. However, if the promoted MB adsorption onto TiO_2 involves an increase in the initial degradation rate, it would show that the PCD rate of MB in both MgCl_2 and CaCl_2 aqueous solutions are essentially equal because the salt concentration is generally below 3 M in practice.

The results of our study showed that the adsorption of MB onto nanosized TiO_2 particles in aqueous solutions containing high MgCl_2 or CaCl_2 concentrations was strongly influenced by the salt concentration. It has also been demonstrated that the adsorption still existed at very high concentration (6 M) due to the presence of neutral sites on the TiO_2 surface configuration. Both dye dissociation and polarity influenced the final adsorption equilibrium for a certain concentration range (≥ 0.5 M). The ionic association was proposed to explain why the adsorption rate dropped rapidly in the concentration range from 3 to 5 M and increased slightly with increasing temperature at salt concentrations above 3 M. This study also highlights the difference between Mg^{2+} and Ca^{2+} within the studied concentration range (3–5 M). In addition, our

results suggest that if the ionic dye concentration is much less than that of the ions and TiO_2 in an aqueous solution, the influence of the electrical properties of the dye on the solution system could be ignored.

Experimental

Reagent and material : Analytically pure reagents were obtained for MB (Tianjin Kemel Scientific and Technological Development, Inc., China), CaCl_2 (Liaoning Jiacheng Fine Chemical, Inc., China), and anhydrous MgCl_2 (Wuhan Tianyun Salinity Product, Inc., China). Nanosized TiO_2 (Shanghai Jingchun Reagent, Inc., China) consisting of a mixture of 98% anatase and 2% rutile with a particle size of 30 nm and specific surface of $50 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$, as provided by the manufacturer, was obtained. A $0.22 \mu\text{m}$ filter membrane for a water system (Xiamen Lulong Biotech, Inc., China) was used as the filter, and the water was distilled and deionised before use.

General procedure : The adsorption of MB onto TiO_2 was accomplished in a 500 ml vessel with a double envelope. The water temperature was held constant using a thermostat, and the water was recirculated through the double envelop from a thermostated bath using a pump. Mixing was performed using a VCY-1500S ultrasonic dispersion instrument (Shanghai Sonxi Ultrasonic Instrument, Inc., China).

The adsorption experiments were conducted in the dark by mixing a series of 300 ml aqueous solutions containing 10 mg L^{-1} MB, 2 g L^{-1} TiO_2 and varying salt concentrations. The amount of MB was determined by TOC measurement. For every original sample, the TOC was measured using a Rosemount DC-85A (Rosemount Analytical, Inc., USA). Samples were collected from the vessel in due order. The collected samples were then filtered through a microfiltration membrane for 1 min to separate the TiO_2 particles. The TOC of the filtered solutions was also measured. The molar conductivity of the studied salt concentration range was measured using a DDS-801-S conductivity instrument (Anhui Saiké Environment, Inc., China) and calculated.

The rate of MB adsorption for each sample was calcu-

lated from the following expression :

$$\eta (\eta_e) = \frac{C_0 - C_1}{C_0} \times 100\%$$

where η and η_e is the rate of adsorption and adsorption equilibrium of MB, respectively; C_0 and C_1 are the initial and filtered amount of MB, respectively.

Each experiment was repeated in triplicate to ensure the reproducibility of the data.

UV-Vis analysis : The UV-Vis light absorbances of the solutions and suspensions were measured using a UV2550 UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Shimadzu, Inc., Japan). The aggregation behaviour of the TiO₂ particle suspensions was examined for typical salt concentration ranges in the presence of MB using a UV-Vis spectrometer by monitoring any absorbance changes in the transmitted light ($\lambda = 308$ nm). All of the samples in the absorption spectrophotometric experiments were agitated for 60 min before being placed in the UV-Vis instrument.

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